

User Guide – Dashboard on Foodborne Outbreaks

© European Food Safety Authority, 2024

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. Introduction	3
2. Structure of the dashboard	3
3. Functionalities of the dashboard.....	6
3.1 Filtering	6
3.1.1 Filtering in the filter area	6
3.1.2 Filtering in the map.....	7
3.1.3 Filtering in detailed dashboards	7
3.2 Interaction with graphs	8
3.2.1 Graph types	8
3.2.2 Tooltip information	11
3.2.3 Graph legend	14
3.2.4 Maximize graphs	15
3.2.5 Sorting data.....	16
3.2.6 Data feature menu.....	17
3.2.7 Visualize data in tabular form ('show data' option)	20
3.2.8 Export of data and graphs	22

1. INTRODUCTION

This user guide describes the content and functionalities of the dashboard on foodborne outbreaks (FBO) and provides detailed indications to make full use of this interactive tool.

The FBO dashboard is designed to interactively visualise the foodborne outbreak data reported each year to EFSA by EU Member States and other reporting countries. It shows metric values such as number of outbreaks, human cases, hospitalisations, and deaths, grouped by one or more attributes into separate friendly visualisations. Information on the following attributes is available in the dashboard: reporting year, EU and non-EU, strength of evidence, type of outbreak, reporting country, causative agent, food vehicle and place of exposure. To optimize the data visualisation in the dashboard, different levels of aggregation are defined for some of these attributes (i.e. causative agents, food vehicles and places of exposure).

In the EFSA dashboard, the foodborne outbreaks data (since 2019) and related statistics can be displayed interactively using charts, graphs, and maps. The main statistics can also be visualised (and downloaded) in a tabular format.

2. STRUCTURE OF THE DASHBOARD

The dashboard on foodborne outbreaks is composed of the following seven pages on:

1. Cover page.
2. Causative agents.
3. Reporting countries.
4. Time trends.
5. Food vehicles.
6. Food vehicles and causative agents.
7. Places of exposure.

The user can browse the different pages using the tabs located at the top of the dashboard (Figure 1). The selected tab is highlighted in bold, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Screenshot of tabs of the dashboard pages

All the dashboard pages (except for the cover page) have a common structure, consisting of the title (Figure 2) and the caution icon (Figure 3), the filter area (Figure 4), the main statistics area (Figure 5), the graphical area (Figure 6), and the footer area (Figure 7).

The **page title** is located at the top side of each dashboard page (Figure 2), just below the main dashboard title.

Figure 2: Screenshot of dashboard page title

Under the page title, the **'caution' icon** (Figure 3) could be visualised, to show relevant information about data interpretation. Users can access the detailed message just clicking on the icon , or on the "Caution in data interpretation" text.

Figure 3: Screenshot of 'caution' icon

Figure 4 shows a screenshot of the **filter area** located under the page title. Users can select one or more terms in each filter to retrieve a particular set of data. Some filters (i.e. Reporting year) available in the different pages are associated with an **'information' icon**, which provides information about the specific filters. Users can access the detailed message just clicking on the 'information' icon.

Figure 4: Screenshot of the filter area showing some of the filters included.

Figure 5 shows a screenshot of the **main statistics area** (e.g. the number of countries, outbreaks, cases, hospitalisation, deaths). These values depend on the filters applied in the page.

Figure 5: Screenshot of the main statistics area

The central part of each dashboard page is dedicated to the **graphical area** (Figure 6), which contains different types of charts and may also contain summary tables of the relevant statistics. Data visualised in the graphs (and tables) depends on the filters' selection. The user can select one or more terms in each filter, to retrieve a particular set of data. All graphs provide some interaction tools that are described in detail in this manual.

Figure 6: Screenshot of the graphical area

At the bottom of the dashboard page there is the **footer area** (Figure 7), which contains additional information, as well as the icons with links to the EU One Health Zoonoses Report, user guide and the EFSA story map on Brucella.

On 1 February 2020, the United Kingdom became a third country. Data from the United Kingdom are included in the EU statistics for 2019...[\(read more\)](#)
According to [Directive 2003/99/EC](#) reporting information of foodborne and waterborne outbreaks is mandatory for EU Member States.
Validated data on foodborne outbreaks displayed in the dashboard were extracted from the EFSA zoonoses database on 1 December 2024.
Please note that the data visualised are affected by the selected filters. If you have any questions on this dashboard, please contact zoonoses@efsa.europa.eu

Figure 7: Screenshot of the footer area

3. FUNCTIONALITIES OF THE DASHBOARD

3.1 FILTERING

Different filters can be selected to retrieve a particular set of data. The selected filters work only within each dashboard page.

The user can do a single or multiple selection of the filter items. When one or more filter options are selected, the page refreshes and graphs report only data satisfying the selected filters. If no data is available for the selected filters, the graphical area shows the following message: "Filter excludes all data."

3.1.1 FILTERING IN THE FILTER AREA

In the filter area of each dashboard page the user finds drop-down filters (Figure 8); by clicking on the icon of each filter, a list of terms is visualised; one or more options can be selected; by clicking the OK button the user confirms the selection and the drop-down list will be closed.

Figure 8 shows a screenshot of the drop-down list available for the filter 'Reporting year'.

Figure 8: Screenshot of the drop-down list available for the filter 'reporting year'

Figure 9 shows in green the filters available in each dashboard page.

FILTERS	DASHBOARD PAGES						
	Cover page	Causative agents	Reporting countries	Time trends	Food vehicles	Food vehicles and causative agents	Places of exposure
REPORTING YEAR							
EU AND NON-EU							
REPORTING COUNTRY							
STRENGTH OF EVIDENCE							
TYPE OF OUTBREAK							
FOOD VEHICLE							
PLACE OF EXPOSURE							
CAUSATIVE AGENT GROUP							
CAUSATIVE AGENT							

Green: filter available.

Figure 9: Filters available in each of the dashboard page

3.1.2 FILTERING IN THE MAP

In the dashboard pages on 'Reporting countries' a specific country, or more than one country (using the CTRL key), can be selected by clicking on the map. This produces a dynamic selection on the graph on the right side of the dashboard page, as shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10: Screenshot of the filter for reporting countries selected on the map.

When selecting the countries using the map, the selection does not apply to the main statistics, but only affects the table included in the same page.

3.1.3 FILTERING IN DETAILED DASHBOARDS

The detailed pages available in the Causative agents, Food vehicles and Places of exposure pages, offers additional filters (other than those available in the filtering area, already presented in Section 3.1.1) displayed in a vertical section, located on the left side of the page.

The filter options can be selected by checking the related box or by selecting the "only" option, visualised on the right side of a single option when hovering the label with the mouse.

Figure 11 shows, as an example, the screenshot of the filter 'causative agent group' available in the detailed dashboard on causative agents.

Figure 11: Screenshot of the filter 'causative agent group' available in the detailed dashboard on causative agents

3.2 INTERACTION WITH GRAPHS

3.2.1 GRAPH TYPES

Several types of graphs are available in the graphical area of the different dashboard's pages, as listed and described below.

The **bar chart** presents horizontal or vertical bars of different lengths, showing the value of a metric grouped by a specific attribute (see Figure 12).

Figure 12: Example of bar chart

The **vertical bar chart** shows the lines indicating the values of one metric over a 5-year period (i.e. number of hospitalisations over years). An example of line chart included in the dashboard page 'Time trends' is shown in Figure 13.

Figure 13: Example of vertical bar chart included in the dashboard page 'Time trends'.

The **donut chart** shows slices in a circle where the size of each slice matches with the value of the variable measured. An example of donut chart included in the dashboard is shown in Figure 14.

Figure 14: Example of donut chart

The **bubble chart** shows a multi-variable graph where a cartesian coordinate system plots points along a grid where the X and Y axis are separate variables and for each point is assigned a label or category (either displayed on a legend). Each plotted point then represents a third variable.

Figure 15 shows the bubble chart included in the dashboard page 'Reporting countries', where each coloured bubble represents the number of human cases per causative agents, by reporting country.

Figure 15: Bubble chart included in the dashboard page 'Reporting countries.'

The **Map** included in the dashboard pages 'Reporting countries,' shows the geographic distribution of outbreak reporting rate in EU Member States and other reporting countries (Figure 16).

Figure 16: Map of the outbreak reporting rate available in the dashboard page 'Reporting countries'

Users can select one or multiple countries using three different selection tools , placed on the top left side of the map; additionally, a country can be also search just typing the name in the search area

Zoom-in and zoom-out tools are available on the right side of the map (plus/minus icon)

Users can visualise the information shown in the graphs also in a **tabular form (grid)**.

Figure 17 shows an example of grid, where data are presented in a tabular form (see also Section 3.2.7)

Causative agent	Outbreaks	Human cases	Hospitalisations	Deaths
Unknown	2,698	16,765	394	7
Salmonella	1,041	7,215	1,460	8
Bacterial toxins, unspecified	636	5,594	181	2
Norovirus and other calicivirus	347	7,717	100	2
Bacillus cereus toxins	308	3,216	66	2
Campylobacter	256	1,103	83	0
Staphylococcus aureus toxins	139	2,270	149	4
Histamine and...	100	512	44	0

Figure 17: Example of data shown in tabular form (grid)

3.2.2 TOOLTIP INFORMATION

Several types of interaction/functionalities are available in the graphical area of the different dashboard's pages, as listed and described in the next sections of the document.

The **tooltip** information is visible when the mouse pointer is placed on graph element and shows more detailed data (e.g. Reporting year, Number of sampling units tested and Number of positive units).

An Example of tooltip message is shown in Figure 18, 19, 20 and 21.

Figure 18: Example of tooltips in a bar chart

Figure 19: Example of tooltips in a vertical bar chart

Figure 20: Example of tooltips in a map

Figure 21: Example of tooltips in a donut graph

3.2.3 GRAPH LEGEND

The **legend**, placed on the right or bottom side of the graphs, describes the variables shown (see Figure 22 and 23).

Figure 22: Example of legend in a bar chart

Figure 23: Example of legend in a horizontal percent chart

Users can minimize or hide the legend of a graph, by clicking on the following icons (also shown in Figure 24):

to minimize the legend

to hide the legend

When the legend is hidden, users must right click on graphical area and select the **Show Legend** option, to display legend again.

Figure 24: Example of interaction with legend options

3.2.4 MAXIMIZE GRAPHS

On the upper right of each graph the user can find two important icons, which allow maximising the graph (Figure 25) and showing the data in a tabular form (Section 3.2.7, Figures 34 and 35).

The **Maximize** option can be enabled by clicking the icon visible on the upper right side of the graph (see Figure 25). After the selection, the graph will be shown in full-page mode.

Please note that the icon becomes visible only when the mouse pointer is moved over the graph.

Figure 25: Example of maximise option.

3.2.5 SORTING DATA

The **sorting data** option can be activated on X or Y axes, to show data in ascending or descending mode. The graph visualisation will change depending on the sorting option selected.

Users can order the information shown in the x-axis, using the sorting menu by right clicking on the x-axis label.

Figures 26 and 27 show an example of the ascending and descending ordering, respectively, applied on n sampling units tested shown in the x-axis.

Figure 26: Example of x-axis ascending sorting

Figure 27: Example of x-axis descending sorting

In the same way, users can order the information shown in the y-axis, using the sorting option by right clicking on the y-axis label. Figure 28 shows an example of ascending order applied to Causative agent. In this case, the ascending order will order values alphabetically.

Figure 28: Example of y-axis sorting applied on Number of outbreaks by causative agent.

It's important to note that when the chart displays values grouped by an attribute (for example, the number of human cases by reporting country, grouped by causative agent), the ascending or descending order feature is applied only to the first value of the attribute in the grouping (for example, the first causative agent).

3.2.6 DATA FEATURE MENU

Users can access the data feature menu, by right clicking on one of the elements in bar or line charts. The data feature menu allows selecting the '**Keep only**', '**Exclude**', '**Show data**' or '**Data labels**' options.

Figure 29 shows an example of data feature menu in a bar chart.

Figure 29: Example of data feature menu in a bar chart.

The '**Keep only**' option excludes all items in the graph, except the one selected (see Figure 30).

Figure 30: Example of 'keep only' option applied to 'Domestic premises' place of exposure.

The '**Exclude**' option excludes the selected item from the graph (see Figure 31 where the "Domestic premises" item was excluded).

Figure 31: Example of 'exclude' option applied to 'Domestic premises' place of exposure

To cancel the filters applied using "exclude" or "keep only" options, use the icon available on the upper left side of the graph, and then select one of the "clear" options listed. Please note that the icon becomes visible only when the mouse pointer is moved over the graph. See Figure 32 for more details.

Figure 32: Example of filters removal

The **'Show data'** option opens a pop-up window showing data related to the item selected, which can be exported.

Figure 33 shows an example of data option applied to the 'Domestic premises' data.

Figure 33: Example of show data option applied to 'Domestic premises' data (graph available in the dashboard page 'Places of exposure').

The **'Data labels'** option shows the numeric values for each item in the graph. This option is enabled by default when the data is loaded.

3.2.7 VISUALIZE DATA IN TABULAR FORM ('SHOW DATA' OPTION)

The **'show data'** option can be enabled by clicking the icon visible on the upper right side of the graph (see Figure 34).

This option will return a tabular form of the data visualized in the graph (see Figure 35); the data shown are affected by the filter selection applied on the dashboard pages.

Figure 34: Example of 'show data' option (icon)

Figure 35: Example of 'Show Data' option (tabular form)

After the selection of the 'Show Data' option and the visualisation of the data in a tabular form, data can be ordered by clicking on the column's name. A triangle icon will indicate the type of ordering (ascending or descending). Figure 36 shows an example of ordering applied to the second column of the data table.

Show Data ? x

10 Rows + ↗

Strength of evidence	Reporting year	Outbreaks	Human cases	
Strong evidence	2020	276	6,092	
Strong evidence	2021	383	7,524	
Strong evidence	2022		10,759	
Strong evidence	2023		11,612	
Strong evidence	2019		17,115	
Weak evidence	2020		15,921	
Weak evidence	2021		26,291	
Weak evidence	2019	5,129	38,339	
Weak evidence	2023	5,177	41,673	
Weak evidence	2022	5,346	40,012	

Close

Figure 36: Example of data ordering

3.2.8 EXPORT OF DATA AND GRAPHS

Several types of data export are available in the graphical area of the different dashboard's pages. Users can download data as described below.

After the selection of '**Show Data**' option (see Figure 37), data can be exported in three different formats:

- Excel
- PDF
- CSV (option labelled "Data")

The export data option includes all the attributes originally shown in the table and any information added by the user. Please note that the export action depends on the filter terms selected on the dashboard page.

Figure 37 shows an example of data export.

Strength of evidence	Reporting year	Outbreaks	Human cases
Strong evidence	2020	276	
Strong evidence	2021	383	
Strong evidence	2022	525	
Strong evidence	2023	614	
Strong evidence	2019	811	
Weak evidence	2020	2,891	26,291
Weak evidence	2021	3,706	26,291
Weak evidence	2019	5,129	38,339
Weak evidence	2023	5,177	41,673
Weak evidence	2022	5,346	40,012

Figure 37: Example of data export

After the selection of the data export function, users can save information selecting the target output file (Excel, PDF, CSV).

The 'export as pdf' option is currently not working for maps. This functionality will be fixed as soon as possible.